

METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF COMPETENCES OF PUPILS' INTEREST IN NATIONAL CRAFTS BASED ON THE CLUSTER APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of the cluster approach in the practical processes of technology and career orientation, and the method of forming the competences of students' interest in national crafts based on this.*

Keywords: *technology, career guidance, cluster approach, national craft, independent assessment.*

In today's conditions, due to the expansion of production areas, the complexity of economic relations, and the acceleration of scientific and technical development, every minute of working time is precious. Therefore, it is necessary to strictly adhere to internal procedures and work discipline, starting with school education. For this, favorable conditions should be created in the process of technology and education. In this case, it is necessary to approach pupils with high demands along with teaching, using methods such as explaining, persuading, encouraging, and showing an example. When there are deviations in pupils' interactions, it is necessary to explain (show) how they should behave in this or that case with positive examples. As a result of the systematic and strict requirements of the teacher, the students gradually get used to the clear and conscious implementation of various rules and methods of work. They are used to maintaining work order, keeping the workplace in an exemplary manner, and taking care of tools. One of the important conditions for preparing pupils for independent work and mode of life is to establish discipline and gradually achieve its maintenance.

It is necessary to educate students to care for society and personal property, to have a conscious attitude, and to form a thrifty attitude towards social and personal property. It is also important for them to respect working people, to educate their will and character. One of the most effective ways to educate students about social property awareness is to involve them in the repair of common work equipment and tools. It is necessary to teach students to save various materials economically, to take care of equipment, work clothes and to educate manners, discipline and high work culture. In the process of preparing students for work and profession, education of a high level of work culture is one of the main tasks of a teacher-coach. It is necessary to constantly and consistently educate the pupils about the beauty of work, a deep and comprehensive understanding of human relationships. The elegance of labor begins with the preparation of simple items and is manifested directly in the labor process and its results.

During class and extracurricular activities, the teacher should always emphasize the beauty of a well-made handicraft, the correctness of detail processing, and the accuracy of the student's labor movements. In conversations with students, the teacher should highlight and encourage the fact that honest work should become the main content of living in our society, and this should

serve to form their ability to work creatively. In our society, the beauty of work is inextricably linked with spiritual and material stimulation.

Technology and Vocational Science differs from other academic subjects in that it is an embodied subject. Therefore, in the process of organizing this education, pupils widely apply the knowledge they have received from general education subjects. In addition, this education itself combines a number of fields (processing of various materials, agriculture, industry, cooking, gas science, etc.) in its system. Each of these areas is considered to be different areas of production activities that are not similar to each other. Teachers, coaches, leaders and other officials involved in the organization of technology and career guidance of young people should be able to distinguish the specifics of these trainings.

One of the effective ways to educate students on the basis of folk crafts in technology classes is to teach the art of goldsmithing, because students will be able to create exquisite items with their own hands. Sewing with goldish thread is based on a certain technology. Our pupils can easily learn and use this technology.

As a conclusion, it can be said that the methodology of educating students in technology classes based on folk crafts educates students in self-critical evaluation and tolerance towards shortcomings. In it, the teacher examines the finished product and offers the students to evaluate it independently. The work experience of advanced teachers shows that such a method has an important educational value. Regular practice of determining the quality of the products made by pupils helps them to develop self-control skills and a sense of critical evaluation of their own work. For this, during the rest breaks, at the end of the training, after the analysis of the work results, the teacher-coach should tell the students about the methods used by the advanced and self-sacrificing workers. For such conversations, it is recommended to show the life of masters in local enterprises as an example. Because only high-quality, beautiful, durable products can be competitive in market relations.

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